

Fostering efficiency in data management planning, data management, and quality assurance by developing and applying RDMO extensions

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Executive Summary

Research projects in the Earth System Sciences (ESS) are mostly data-driven and either use data as input for analysis workflows or create data as a main result. Thus, these projects demand a proper data management and related planning, that is core for considering reusability of the data after the end of the project. RDMO (Research Data Management Organizer¹) is a tool for planning and conducting research data management in a structured way. Therefore, RDMO facilitates data management planning and comprises, among others, questionnaires for researchers, tasks management, and reporting options.

Besides the core functionality, RDMO can be extended by implementing plugins and scripts that enable the usage of RDMO for new use cases.

Here, we present three extensions developed in the GeoKur² project: (1) RDMOCatalogBuilder is a script that facilitates the preparation of new questionnaires, which includes an example of a data assurance workflow controlled and documented via RDMO. (2) RDMOViewBuilder tool creates a view from an RDMO catalog to provide a quick overview on available questions and answers (3) RDMO2CKAN is an export function script to facilitate linking tools - a planning and a metadata management tool by reusing specific fields from RDMO to CKAN³, an open source data management system.

¹ <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/>, last access: 29.03.2022

² <https://geokur.geo.tu-dresden.de/>, last access: 29.03.2022

³ <https://ckan.org/>, last access: 13.04.2022

Use Case

In our project GeoKur, we aim to support the curation and quality assurance of Earth System Science (ESS) data sets, focusing on the suitability of geospatial time-series of global land use data by analyzing human-environment relations such as land degradation, biodiversity, human migration and ecosystem services⁴. Within the project three partners collaborate on the two use cases: (1) a team of researchers collects, analyses and provides data, scripts, and related publications, (2) a team of data stewards and software engineers provides discipline-specific guidance, adapted tools, and develops specific methods and tools based on the researcher needs, and (3) a team of data producers applies developed concepts and tools for their workflows.

Here, we describe outcomes of the software engineering team addressing tool support for data management planning, related metadata management, and curation/quality assurance. Our concepts and implementations are based on the following requirements:

- Provide easy-to-use tools for administrators and users that are robust for errors
- Provide the smallest set of tools that is possible to solve the given research data management tasks, e.g. data management, planning, curation
- Provide linked tools to avoid managing redundant information and to foster reusing information, e.g. in data management planning instances and metadata entries
- Support users to manage a complex quality assurance workflow collaboratively
- Support users to export results of the applied quality assurance
- Support curators to monitor quality assurance and curate

Catalog Building for RDMO

The major goal of our proposed python project RDMOCatalogBuilder is to facilitate the technical (but not content-related) elaboration of new catalogs for RDMO and to support administrators by providing automated naming and linking of all relevant elements.

RDMOCatalogBuilder is developed under Apache-2.0 license⁵ and available on GitHub:

<https://github.com/GeoinformationSystems/RDMOCatalogBuilder>

From the user perspective, the core of an RDMO instance is the catalog that implements the questions they should answer. A catalog has a hierarchical structure including sections, question sets, and questions. Additionally, option sets, conditions, and tasks provide mechanisms to manage defined answers, to define restrictions or work items in the RDMO questionnaire. The central part of RDMO's data model is the domain model that links user input and questions. Each answer is stored in an attribute of the domain model. Hence, an attribute is similar to a variable in program code and can be used in conditions and tasks. This results in a powerful, but complex system of questions, options, conditions, and tasks. When RDMO administrators elaborate a new questionnaire, they have to add the required attributes, set up the lists of conditions and options, and implement the catalog structure. The last process includes defining tasks or specific answers

⁴ Egli, Lukas, Fischer, Julia, Groth, Juliane, Della Chiesa, Stefano, & Henzen, Christin. (2022). Data Management Plan for Use Cases of the GeoKur Project on suitability of global land use data to assess relationships between land use, degradation, pollination and human migration. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5992729>

⁵ <http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0>, last access: 31.03.2022

(or the absence of answers). From a technical perspective, the crucial point is the proper linking between attributes, questions, options, conditions, and tasks.

In RDMO, this is enabled via GUI in the management section, but it is still based on manual work. Here, our Python package RDMOCatalogBuilder implements a "write once use multiple times" concept: A json file filled with all necessary information serves as single input for the script that parses the json file and builds five xml files for questions, domain, options, conditions, and tasks. That ensures for each xml file to be implemented in the correct format und facilitates to avoid typos.

Figure 1: RDMO management page for questions (left) with the import button (red mark), exemplary json content (top right), and the xml content produced with RDMOCatalogBuilder (bottom right).

Moreover, the developed RDMOCatalogBuilder generates all necessary links, e.g. it automatically adds proper attributes to the domain for each question following a tree structure with a starting url prefix. Conditions are properly linked to the according attributes, if needed. The structure of the input json file corresponds to the (logical) order of sections, question sets, and questions in the questionnaire. In contrast to the internal RDMO abilities/ordering, the settings of a question, e.g. an option set or a condition, are restructured and written directly below the question itself. By structuring the questions and related items logically, we support managing larger questionnaires, like data management plan (DMP) templates from funders.

In RDMO, the tasks are derived from a questionnaire, but they are not directly included in the questionnaire structure, but ordered below the catalog description in the related json document. The naming and linking is accomplished by the RDMOCatalogBuilder and the resulting xml files can be imported in the RDMO management pages (Figure 1).

In our use case, we use the RDMOCatalogBuilder to create a complex catalog and questionnaire for quality assurance workflows. Here, RDMO serves as collaborative tool to enable researchers to record quality assurance activities and to enable curators to evaluate performed and recorded activities.

View Building for RDMO

The RDMOCatalogBuilder aims to support the development of a new questionnaire. However, an displaying the questionnaire in the RDMO UI is not covered in this tool. RDMO offers a

customizable view functionality for catalogs. Our RDMOViewBuilder addresses these views and provides functionalities to create a view draft from an arbitrary RDMO catalog showing all elements of a questionnaire.

RDMOViewBuilder is developed under Apache-2.0 license and available on GitHub:

<https://github.com/GeoinformationSystems/RDMOViewBuilder>

The views in RDMO provide a comprehensive overview of the whole questionnaire including the answers, or a more selective view on parts of the questionnaire that target specific use cases, e.g. controlling or curation. The user can export a view in different formats, including but not restricted to office suite format, html, or markdown. Building a custom view with the RDMO GUI is challenging, in particular in finding and including proper attributes in the proper form (e.g. single dataset, or a collection of datasets).

Our developed RDMOViewBuilder loads the xml file, either exported from an arbitrary RDMO questionnaire in the management pages, or directly taken from the output of RDMOCatalogBuilder. It preserves the order of sections, question sets, and questions with their titles, texts, help texts, and includes the answers given by users. Moreover, RDMOViewBuilder supports the RDMO administrator by automatically creating an xml file for direct input via the RDMO view management pages.

In RDMO, views contain only one language although catalogs can contain various languages. Therefore, RDMOViewBuilder can optionally build a view for each requested locale. With importing such a view xml file, RDMO creates a complete draft with the appropriate attributes and structures. Based on the project needs, the administrator can then edit the draft, e.g. adding attributes.

In our use case, we use the RDMOViewBuilder to create a comprehensive overview on recorded quality assurance activities. Thus, a curator uses RDMO to monitor the activities and provide specific guidance on where additional information on applied quality assurance concepts is needed and where and how to include more activities.

Exporting Metadata from RDMO to CKAN via Plugin

To foster reusability and to avoid redundancies in case of research data management, linking DMP tools and data management systems (DMS) is essential. Our RDMO2CKAN implements a linking of an RDMO instance and a CKAN instance by automatically creating or updating dataset metadata managed in RDMO to the CKAN.

The RDMO2CKAN plugin is developed under Apache-2.0 license and published under GitHub:

<https://github.com/GeoinformationSystems/RDMO2CKAN>

Researchers are increasingly requested to outline what they plan to do with the data during and after the project funding, e.g. regarding long-term archiving, data managing, or data protection. Such a data management plan (DMP) potentially comprises metadata, e.g. for input data or expected data results that can be used in the data management system. In that case, linking the DMP tool RDMO and the DMS CKAN reduces the amount of work and avoids errors/transfer problems. The RDMO2CKAN plugin is developed as an export plugin for RDMO and provides an export button in the RDMO management section for sending relevant metainformation to the CKAN (Figure 2).

Currently, the export function needs a specific questionnaire (Science_europe_questionnaire.xml; available on the GitHub repository). Within the questions, users are asked to describe input and created data with metadata. By clicking on the "to ckan" button the plugin functionality is triggered. The plugin checks for each dataset that is listed in the DMP instance in RDMO if a metadata set in

the linked CKAN exists. If the metadata set already exists, it will be updated in CKAN. For a new metadata set, the plugin creates a new metadata entry in CKAN and includes the information from the questionnaire.

For the usage of the plugin, the administrator has to consider two aspects: First, the usage of the plugin is limited to the mentioned questionnaire. The questionnaire includes the attributes, which are used by the plugin to create or update meta information. Second, the plugin is based on the CKAN API, which needs a valid API token. The token provides access to the related organization defined in the CKAN and must be added to the plugin's source code manually. In future versions we plan to ask for the token e.g. in the questionnaire to enable the export function for various CKAN accounts.

Figure 2: RDMO questionnaire page with adapted Science Europe questionnaire and questions necessary for export to CKAN (left), and project overview page in RDMO (right) with the button “to ckan” (red mark)

In our use case, we use the RDMO2CKAN to foster the provision of DMP instances as living documents. When updating DMP instances during the project, the metadata of related datasets can be automatically updated in the linked DMS.

When applying the developed plugins as part of our GeoKur research data infrastructure, we can provide tool-supported data management planning, quality assurance workflows, and curation by only providing, administrating and maintaining two (open-source) tools.